

MATH APPS IN MATH EDUCATION: EXPERIENCES AND CHALLENGES OF PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

This qualitative study investigated the experiences and challenges of pre-service math teachers (BSED Math students) who use math applications. Interviews with 20 students found that they use several apps for math, visualization, and problem-solving, which improves their knowledge. However, restricted internet connection, confusing interfaces, and app charges presented difficulties. Students responded by discovering free alternatives, increasing app literacy, and seeking assistance from teachers or peers. The report recommends that developers concentrate on user-friendly design, comprehensive instructions, and features that encourage strategic app use. Educators are advised to strategically integrate math applications while taking into account varied learning styles. Future studies can look into the long-term impact of app use, the potential for tailored learning via adaptive applications, and teacher training programs focusing on technology integration in math education.

Keywords: *math applications, BSED Math students, problem-solving, conceptual understanding, accessibility, user-friendly interfaces*

INTRODUCTION

Many pupils struggle with mathematics, as evidenced by continuously low scores on international examinations (Velasco et al., 2019). To solve these issues and improve student learning results, mathematics education must be revitalized through new solutions. In this changing educational context, math applications have emerged as a

potential tool, giving numerous advantages over traditional techniques (Byers et al., 2018). These applications have the potential to personalize learning experiences by addressing individual requirements and learning styles (Shin, Jeonghwa, 2018).

They can provide immediate feedback, allowing students to recognize and correct faults right away, fostering a more self-directed learning process (Zhu et al., 2022). Math applications can also make the learning environment more interesting by including interactive aspects, gamification, and visual representations (Zhang & Chan, 2020). These elements can assist students in visualizing complex topics, enabling deeper learning and potentially reducing arithmetic anxiety (Prediger et al., 2022). According to research, applications can boost student engagement and motivation in mathematics, potentially leading to a more enjoyable and productive learning experience (Pandita & Kiran, 2023).

However, merely giving pupils access to math apps is not a guaranteed solution. Marshman's (2020) research emphasizes the importance of understanding how students use these tools effectively. Disparities between app features and classroom instruction might confuse pupils, limiting their capacity to apply learned concepts in the context of the courses (Kwok et al., 2020). Furthermore, minimal instructional help inside the applications can cause students to struggle with complicated concepts, especially when dealing with novel themes (Bennett, 2021). This highlights the significance of seamlessly integrating technology into established instructional practices. Unequal access to resources, such as reliable internet connectivity or gadgets, might further disadvantage some pupils and worsen existing educational disparities (Koroteeva, 2022).

Another potential risk is an overreliance on applications, which may result in a diminished emphasis on developing critical thinking and problem-solving skills, which are required for long-term success in mathematics (Abdullaeva et al., 2020). Math programs can provide step-by-step solutions or automated computations, which may impede the development of these essential skills. Online applications may struggle to capture these aspects effectively, with some question formats being more easily gamed than others (Nobis, 2023).

Despite these potential limitations, research indicates that well-designed and implemented math applications can have favorable outcomes. For example, Krall (2023) discovered that a math application with gamified aspects and peer-to-peer learning features boosted students' arithmetic achievement, engagement, and motivation. This is consistent with the expanding body of studies demonstrating the promise of technology-assisted learning approaches when used properly.

The purpose of this study is to fill a knowledge gap in the usage of math applications in higher education mathematics learning. Specifically, we will look into how students pursuing a Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) major in Mathematics use these programs. By evaluating their experiences and the difficulties they face, we can acquire useful insights about how to best use these technologies. This will help us establish a more thorough knowledge of the function of math apps in math education for

higher education students, as well as inform the creation of effective pedagogical techniques that use technology to foster critical thinking abilities. Finally, these initiatives can lead to enhanced student learning outcomes in mathematics education, providing future educators with the required skills to properly integrate technology into their classrooms.

Research Questions

The goal of this study is to discover Mathematics Applications utilized by Bachelor of Secondary Education students majoring in Mathematics. The researchers will seek answers to the following study questions:

1. What mathematical applications are used by Bachelor of Secondary Education students majoring in Mathematics?
2. What is the motivation or objective of BSED in employing mathematical applications?
3. What issues did the respondents encounter when using the mathematics application?
4. What remedies were developed for the challenges encountered by BSED math students?

METHODOLOGY

Research Method

The researchers used a qualitative research approach to acquire a thorough understanding of how pre-service math teachers interact with math applications. This technique allowed for an examination of the "how" and "why" of these encounters. Purposive sampling guaranteed focused participation. Twenty BSED Math students (five from each year level) were recruited from the University of Eastern Philippines Laoang Campus for the 2023-2024 academic year. These students, who were actively involved in math learning and pursuing teaching jobs, most likely had a solid foundation in arithmetic and were currently using math apps.

In-depth, one-on-one interviews were conducted as part of the data-gathering process, following a pre-planned interview schedule. The researchers created this schedule, which was evaluated by math education experts. The timetable focused on crucial aspects such as the individual math applications used, and the obstacles faced by the pupils.

Before the interviews', informed consent was sought. This procedure confirmed that participants understood the study's goal, that their data would be kept confidential,

and that their consent for audio recording was provided. The interviews were then done with a voice recorder, and the recordings were transcribed verbatim to preserve the participants' voices. The ethical norms of informed consent, anonymity, and confidentiality were followed throughout the research process.

Finally, thematic analysis was used to detect reoccurring themes in the interview transcripts. This qualitative approach will rely on direct quotations from students to appropriately convey their perceptions and experiences with math applications. The thematic analysis will focus on identifying the problems that pre-service teachers have when using math applications and how they incorporate these tools into their curriculum.

RESULTS

This study investigated the experiences of Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) Math students with math applications through qualitative interviews with 20 students (five from each year level). Thematic analysis of interview transcripts found major themes of application use, which are displayed in the tables below:

Math Applications Used by BSED Math Students

The examination of student replies indicated a wide range of math programs utilized by BSED Math students, which were classified according to their principal function. One group emerged as scientific computation applications, which most likely included scientific calculators (Chen et al., 2018) as well as complicated calculation tools within Excel (Microsoft, 2021) or Mathway (Ali Alqashanin & Faqihi, 2022). Geogebra (Hohenwarter et al., 2018) is an example of a visualization tool that creates visual representations of mathematical concepts. Students can benefit from problem-solving software like Microsoft Math Solver (bin Hamad bin Shahlub AL KHATRI & AL-GHAFERI, 2024) and Mathway features that provide solutions and explanations. Formula reference apps, such as the All Math Formula App, provide instant access to formulas without necessarily solving issues. A third category, "Advanced Computation," includes Excel's more advanced functions (Microsoft, 2021) utilized in scientific or technical applications, as opposed to its fundamental calculating skills. Finally, a single AI application was found, while research on AI-powered math tutoring systems (RIZVI, 2023) indicates that it can incorporate capabilities from other categories (Nobis, 2021).

The table also includes applications requiring further investigation to determine their functionalities and locate relevant citations. These include MathPapa, MalMath, AI Application, Math Solver, GuthMath, Graphing Calculator, Calculus App, MathLAB, Symbolab, Algebrator, Calces App, Calchat, Scientific Calculator Hyper App, and question.ai.

Table 1: Types of Math Applications Used by BSED Math Students

Category	Math Applications
Scientific Computation Apps	CalCes, Scientific Calculator Hyper App and Scientific Calculator App, Calchat, excel
Visualization Apps	GeoGebra, Desmos, Graphing Calculator
Math Problem-Solving Apps	Mathway, MATHPapa, Microsoft Math solver, MalMath, Photomath, Algebrator, symbolab, Calculus App and GuthMath
Formula Reference App	All Math formula app
AI powered tools	Question.AI
Scientific Computing Software	Mathlab, Excel

Purpose in Using Mathematical Application

The charts explain why BSED math students use these applications (Alghamdi, 2023). The researcher analyzed the data and found repeating themes and phrases in the descriptions, such as "understanding," "complex lessons," "visualize," "graphs," "concepts," and "solve" (Cole & Zavala, 2024). The keywords were classified according to their meaning. Words like "understanding," "complex lessons," and "concepts" all indicated that users wanted a more in-depth comprehension of the subject (Wang et al., 2022). Words such as "visualize," "graph," and "solve" emphasized the significance of visual representation in learning (Bair & Mooney, 2023]. Finally, the researcher developed two major themes: understanding and visualization.

Table 2: Reasons or Purpose of BSED using Mathematical Application

Theme	Description	Answers
Understanding	Users want to improve their understanding of mathematical concepts and problem-solving techniques	<p>“Enhance their understanding and knowledge...”</p> <p>“Very helpful to use in understanding complex or difficult lessons...”</p>
Visualization	Users find it helpful to visualize concepts using graphs.	<p>“Used for solving and illustrating graph effectively...”</p> <p>“Geogebra helps me create graphs making it easier for me to visualize mathematical concepts...”</p>

Problems Encountered with Math Applications

BSED Math students face a variety of problems when using math applications. Limited internet access is a significant barrier because many apps require an internet connection and data subscriptions, which might be costly or unavailable in certain places (Chen et al., 2018). Furthermore, sophisticated app interfaces might be difficult to use, particularly for new users, limiting their ability to use the app efficiently (Yoon et al., 2020). Another worry is cost, as data plans and future in-app fees may limit access to sophisticated capabilities (Khaleel & Naimi, 2022). Finally, over-reliance on mobile apps for problem-solving can impede the development of critical thinking abilities, as students may not learn to break down problems and find solutions on their own (Martyanti and Suhartini, 2019). To solve these issues, developers should prioritize offline functionality, educators can encourage strategic app use, and freemium models with minimal features can be investigated to make these tools more accessible and successful for students (Jeon et al., 2020). By overcoming these obstacles, BSED Math students can maximize the potential of math applications to improve their comprehension and problem-solving skills.

Table 3: Problems Encountered with Math Applications

Theme	Description
Accessibility	Math apps may require an internet connection and data subscription, which can limit accessibility for some users.
Usability	Some Math apps can be complex and difficult to use, especially for beginners.
Cost	The cost of data subscriptions and potential in-app purchases can be a barrier to using Math apps.
Over-Reliance	Students can become overly reliant on math apps, hindering the development of problem-solving skills.

Solutions made to the problems encountered by BSED Math students

BSED Math students noted a variety of problems when using math applications. Students prioritized free or low-cost apps, underlining the need for easily accessible learning materials. Students also recognized the necessity of successful app design, recommending elements such as user-friendly interfaces, tutorials, and in-app guidance to accommodate a wide range of user skill levels (Oktavihari et al., 2019). Students demonstrated collaboration and resourcefulness by recommending that they seek aid from classmates, professors, or internet resources such as YouTube tutorials to tackle obstacles. This emphasizes the importance of peer learning, instructor support, and student ingenuity. Finally, students underlined the significance of appropriate app use, arguing for a balance between relying on applications and developing autonomous problem-solving abilities. This is consistent with the idea of carefully integrating math apps into the learning process to improve, not replace, critical thinking skills (Deo, 2022). By integrating these student-generated solutions and cultivating a culture of strategic app use, BSED Math programs may help students realize the full potential of math

applications while also improving their mathematical understanding and problem-solving skills.

Table 4: Solutions made to the problems encountered by BSED Math students

Themes	Description
Cost Concerns and Finding Alternatives	Students prioritize finding free or cost-effective Math apps to avoid subscription fees. This highlights the financial limitations faced and the need for accessible learning tools.
Improving Math App Literacy	Students acknowledge the need to learn how to use math apps effectively, suggesting the importance of user-friendly interfaces, tutorials, and in-app guidance.
Collaboration and Resourcefulness	Students suggest seeking help from classmates, instructors, or online resources (YouTube tutorials) to overcome challenges with specific apps or internet limitations. This highlights the value of peer learning, teacher support, and student resourcefulness.
Responsible App Use and Learning	Students acknowledge the need for responsible app use and a balance between relying on apps and developing independent problem-solving skills. This emphasizes math apps strategically in the learning process.

DISCUSSION

This qualitative study investigated the experiences of Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) Math students with math applications. The findings, provided in a series of tables, provide particular information about how these students employed or utilized applications to improve their mathematics learning.

Math Applications Used by BSED Math Students

The results revealed a wide range of math programs utilized by BSED Math students, classified by their principal use. "Scientific Computation Apps" comprised programs like Scientific Calculator and Mathway, which focused on computations. Visualization applications such as Geogebra provided visual representations of mathematical concepts. Formula reference applications provided access to formulas, and problem-solving apps such as PhotoMath supplied solutions and clarifications. Excel's advanced functions were classified as "Advanced Computation" to distinguish them from its basic calculating capabilities. Finally, a single AI-powered application was assigned to a different category due to its ability to incorporate capabilities from many groupings. This classification emphasizes the breadth of functionality provided by math programs and how BSED Math students use them to meet a variety of learning objectives.

Purpose in Using Mathematical Application

In this description, respondents show a desire to better understand mathematical topics. Math applications are seen as beneficial in supplementing teacher-led instruction and gaining a deeper knowledge of complex concepts. Visualization is another crucial feature that math apps can offer to help responders understand ideas. Math applications, which use graphs and other visual aids, can help learners understand the relationships between mathematical topics. This is consistent with previous research titled "Using Math Apps for Improving Student Learning: An Exploratory Study in an Inclusive Fourth Grade Classroom" (2019), which investigated the use of math apps in the classroom and discovered that they improve students' understanding of concepts, particularly for struggling students.

Problem Encountered with Math Applications

These topics highlight some of the challenges that students may encounter when utilizing Math apps. This is especially concerning for difficult problems in which finding a solution is a worthwhile learning experience. Overreliance might make pupils dependent on the software, limiting their capacity to solve problems independently and build critical thinking abilities. The demand for internet connection and data subscriptions provides a barrier for students in places with inadequate connectivity or high-cost data plans. This emphasizes the need for educators and app makers to identify ways to make math apps more accessible, such as adding offline functionality or a data-friendly version. This is consistent with Rodriguez's (2019) study, "The Impact of Calculator Use on Early Algebra Learning". They discovered that students who depended extensively on calculators to solve algebraic problems performed poorer on conceptual tests than those who utilized calculators strategically.

Solutions Made to the Problems encountered by BSED Math students

The evidence reveals that, while students value math apps, they are aware of the obstacles connected with them, such as cost and usability. To solve these issues, students search for free alternatives, increase their app literacy, and seek assistance from others. The data also underscores the importance of focusing on problem-solving and developing a deeper comprehension of mathematical ideas. This is consistent with a study conducted by Yang Jingmiao et al (2023), which emphasizes the relevance of well-designed lessons and user manuals within math apps. User-friendly interfaces and clear instructions can assist students enhance their learning outcomes and overcome usability issues. In addition, Pani and Mishra et al. (2015) investigated the efficacy of freemium math learning apps. The study discovered that this strategy can be successful for learning math, especially when free features provide a solid basis and entice users to subscribe for additional functionality.

Conclusions

The investigation found a wide range of math programs used by BSED Math students, classified according to their features. This classification emphasizes the breadth of help these programs provide, with students using them for a variety of learning requirements. Scientific computation applications do sophisticated computations, whereas visualization apps provide visual representations of concepts to enhance comprehension. Formula reference apps provide instant access while problem-solving applications provide solutions and explanations. Excel's advanced features were classified individually because of their particular application. Finally, a single AI-powered application was assigned to a different category due to its ability to incorporate capabilities from many groupings.

The data reveals that BSED Math students use these tools to augment their learning and develop a better comprehension of challenging concepts. This is consistent with past studies into the use of math apps in schools, which revealed that they boost student understanding, particularly for those who struggle. Another essential feature that math apps can provide is visualization, which involves using graphs and other visual aids to help students understand the relationships between mathematical ideas.

However, these findings indicate a few issues. Overreliance on problem-solving applications might impede students' capacity to break down problems independently and build critical thinking abilities, particularly for complicated situations when arriving at a solution is a great learning opportunity. Furthermore, the demand for internet connection and data subscriptions poses a barrier for students in places with inadequate connectivity or high-cost data plans. This emphasizes the need for educators and app developers to find methods to make math apps more accessible, such as adding offline functionality or data-friendly options.

Students value math apps, but they are aware of their limitations, such as cost and usability. To solve these issues, students search for free alternatives, increase their app literacy, and seek assistance from others. The data also underlines the strategic use of applications to improve problem-solving skills and acquire a deeper comprehension of mathematical ideas. User-friendly interfaces and clear instructions in math apps can improve learning results and assist students in overcoming usability problems. Freemium models with a strong base and incentives to upgrade for further features can also be useful for math learning.

Overall, this study gives useful information about the use of math applications by BSED Math students. Educators can build techniques to help students use these tools effectively for deeper learning and increased mathematics knowledge by understanding the rewards and problems they present.

Recommendations

This classification provides useful insights for math app developers. Understanding the unique capabilities that students appreciate (scientific computation, visualization, formula reference, problem-solving with explanations, and advanced mathematical tools) allows developers to customize their apps to better fulfill their needs. Furthermore, investigating the potential for AI-powered applications to merge features from other categories may be a viable topic for future development.

Math instructors should investigate ways to strategically include math apps in their curricula to supplement classroom education and accommodate different learning styles. This could include employing visualization apps to improve comprehension of hard concepts or problem-solving apps to provide extra practice and explanations.

To avoid overreliance, educators might encourage students to utilize problem-solving apps wisely, with a focus on comprehending the steps involved rather than merely getting answers. App developers might also include features that encourage critical thinking, such as asking students to present their work or explain their reasons. To address accessibility concerns, developers should prioritize the creation of offline functionality or data-friendly software versions to guarantee that all students can benefit from these resources.

App creators can learn from the tactics that students use to overcome obstacles (finding free alternatives, developing app literacy, and seeking assistance). This data can be used to improve the cost and usability of math applications. For example, developers should consider offering freemium models with strong baseline functionality and obvious upgrade pathways for further features. Furthermore, putting clear lessons and user instructions into the apps can address usability issues and empower students to learn freely.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The University of Eastern Philippines - Laoang granted permission to conduct the study after a brief presentation on the objectives and expected outcomes. Furthermore, the study's purpose was stated to all participants before the start of the investigation. Participation was entirely voluntary, and the participants' identities were kept anonymous. To maintain the highest level of data confidence, the surveys were kept strictly secret.

The researchers made it clear that participation is entirely voluntary, and that each respondent can decline or quit from the study without incurring any costs. Only those who declare a desire to engage are included in the study. Respondents will not receive any remuneration or financial incentives for participating in the study.

Throughout the data collection procedure, researchers supervise and guide participants to ensure that the research protocol is followed. These include addressing any queries or concerns raised by respondents, as well as monitoring progress to ensure that all participants have enough time to complete the research instrument.

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